

Supplementary Information:
**State- and time-resolved observation of ultrafast intermolecular
proton transfer in hydrated biomolecules**

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Suppl. Note 1. Cartesian coordinates for equilibrium structure of hydrated pyrrole complex

Atom	Coordinates (Å)		
	X	Y	Z
C	1.478335294	0.078351387	-0.4177661
N	0.212228677	-0.017283579	0.094176782
C	0.276245656	-0.106449927	1.459140605
C	1.601004533	-0.06630986	1.825985444
C	2.364798358	0.050680975	0.633543856
H	1.645116457	0.157724277	-1.477611692
H	3.437133851	0.108531565	0.55547853
H	1.978187536	-0.115444646	2.83324746
H	-0.616654615	-0.187439118	2.053889313
H	-0.637906297	-0.023237609	-0.449810459
O	-2.354014186	-0.088905851	-1.529580978
H	-2.841060486	-0.903010654	-1.688782883
H	-3.005559777	0.61761604	-1.568783879

Suppl. Table 1. Cartesian coordinates for equilibrium structure of hydrated pyrrole complex optimized in neutral singlet ground state using the B3LYP/aug-cc-PVTZ method. This structure was used to calculate the energies in all tables in the paper. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Atom	Coordinates (Å)		
	X	Y	Z
N	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
C	0.000000	0.000000	1.364013
C	1.329190	0.000000	1.873656
C	2.185745	-0.000731	0.707471
C	1.301789	-0.000751	-0.407764
H	-0.917957	0.000001	1.935836
H	1.633688	0.000826	2.912195
H	3.267853	-0.001083	0.687865
H	1.572745	-0.001193	-1.454794
O	-2.262827	0.035478	-2.026245
H	-2.837495	0.828141	-2.028538
H	-2.771695	-0.792135	-2.148168
H	-1.591650	0.007875	-1.278310

Suppl. Table 2. Cartesian coordinates for equilibrium structure of hydrated pyrrole complex optimized in doubly-ionized triplet ground state with the distance constrain between oxygen and nitrogen atoms. The B3LYP/aug-cc-PVTZ method was used. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Suppl. Note 2. Double-ionization potential of hydrated pyrrole complex

Ionized MOs	State	DIP (eV)	Rel. DIP (eV)
HOMO (π) + HOMO-1 (π)	T ₀	24.14	0.00
HOMO (π) + HOMO (π)	S ₁	24.28	0.14
HOMO (π) + HOMO-1 (π)	S ₂	24.80	0.66
HOMO-1 (π) + HOMO-1 (π)	S ₃	26.56	2.42
HOMO (π) + HOMO-2 (σ)	T ₁	28.48	4.33

Suppl. Table 3. Double-ionization potentials (DIP) and relative DIP of pyrrole molecule. EOM-DIP-CCSD/aug-cc-PVDZ method was used. The relative DIP is shifted with respect to the double ionized triplet ground state. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Ionized MOs	State	DIP (eV)	Rel. DIP (eV)	Character
HOMO (π) + HOMO (π)	S ₁	23.41	0.15	two charges localized on pyrrole
HOMO (π) + HOMO-1 (π)	S ₂	23.90	0.64	two charges localized on pyrrole
HOMO (π) + HOMO-4 (σ on water)	S ₃	24.52	1.26	two charges delocalized
HOMO-1 (π) + HOMO-4 (σ on water)	S ₄	25.44	2.17	two charges delocalized
HOMO-1 (π) + HOMO-1 (π)	S ₅	25.64	2.38	two charges localized on pyrrole

Suppl. Table 4. DIP, relative DIP of pyrrole-water cluster and molecular orbitals mostly involved in ionization within the singlet manifold. EOM-DIP-CCSD/aug-cc-PVDZ method was used. The relative DIP is shifted with respect to the double ionized triplet ground state, see Suppl. Table 6. If not stated otherwise, MOs are localized on pyrrole. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

CI configuration	State	Rel. DIP (eV)	Character
222... + 22.2..	S ₁	0.00	two charges localized on pyrrole
22ba..	S ₂	0.33	two charges localized on pyrrole
22.2..	S ₃	0.43	two charges localized on pyrrole
2b2a..	S ₄	1.30	two charges delocalized
2ab2..	S ₅	1.98	two charges delocalized

Suppl. Table 5. Relative DIP in doubly ionized singlet manifold. CASPT2 method and the cc-PVDZ basis set were used. The active space was set to include 6 electrons and 6 MOs. The excitation energy is shifted with respect to the doubly ionized singlet ground state. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Ionized MOs	State	DIP (eV)	Rel. DIP (eV)	Character
HOMO (π) + HOMO-1 (π)	T ₀	23.26	0.00	two charges localized on pyrrole
HOMO (π) + HOMO-4 (σ on water)	T ₁	24.52	1.26	two charges delocalized
HOMO-1 (π) + HOMO-4 (σ on water)	T ₂	25.44	2.17	two charges delocalized
HOMO (π) + HOMO-8 (σ , delocalized)	T ₃	26.82	3.56	two charges delocalized
HOMO (π) + HOMO-7 (σ , delocalized)				
HOMO (π) + HOMO-2 (σ)	T ₄	27.64	4.38	two charges localized on pyrrole

Suppl. Table 6. DIP, relative DIP of pyrrole-water cluster and molecular orbitals mostly involved in ionization within the triplet manifold. EOM-DIP-CCSD/aug-cc-PVDZ method was used. The relative DIP is shifted with respect to the double ionized triplet ground state. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Suppl. Note 3. Nonadiabatic MD in singlet manifold

Both singlet and triplet doubly ionized states are likely to be populated in our experiments, therefore we simulated the dynamics of pyrrole-water cluster in both spin manifolds. Only the triplet multiplicity is discussed in detail in the main text, as the dynamics obtained with different spin manifolds yield almost identical results. For the completeness of the presented simulations, you can find the results of the simulations in singlet manifold (Suppl. Figs. 1-3).

Suppl. Fig. 1. Population evolution of nonadiabatic molecular dynamics simulations. (a) Population evolution of singlet manifold and (b) triplet manifold. The simulations started from the singlet ground state S_1 and triplet ground state T_0 , respectively. Standard errors (SE) of the electronic state populations were estimated using equation $SE = z\sqrt{\frac{1}{N}p_i(t)(1-p_i(t))}$, where N is the number of trajectories, p_i is the electronic state population at a time t and $z = 1.95$ was used to achieve 95% confidence level. The equations is an approximation of confidence interval for multinomial distribution where each trajectory is considered independently at each time. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Suppl. Note 4. Two-dimensional potential energy surface (PES) calculations

The soft PES scan for the proton transfer channel is performed by fixing the intermolecular N-O and O-H distances at each point while optimizing all other coordinates at the CCSD/cc-pVDZ level at each step, with a step size of 0.1 Å. As shown in Suppl. Fig. 4, the light yellow arrows indicate the preferred proton transfer pathway, resulting into two cations ($H_3O^+ + C_4H_4N^+$) that subsequently undergo Coulomb explosion. Similar to the rigid PES scan result shown in Fig. 3a of the main text, the present calculations also indicate that local double ionization in hydrated pyrrole is accompanied by barrierless proton transfer as the N-O distance shortens.

Suppl. Fig. 2. Molecular dynamics simulation diagrams. (a) Reaction channel evolution for surface hopping starting from state S_1 with the localized charge on pyrrole molecule. The channel analysis focused on the direct dissociation channel or PT channel. Other channels, such as dissociation of the hydrogen atom, were not observed. (b)+(c) Evolution of interatomic distances analyzed from the surface hopping simulation in triplet ground state. (b) Distances between O and N atoms (r_{ON}) and (c) distances between O atom and H atom on pyrrole molecule (r_{OH}) as functions of time. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Suppl. Note 5. 800 nm pump-400 nm probe and 400 nm pump-800 nm probe measurements

The time-dependent KER distribution obtained from our two-color pump-probe measurement is presented in Suppl. Fig. 5a. Here, linearly polarized 800 nm and 400 nm laser pulses are used. The positive and negative time delays in Suppl. Fig. 5a correspond to the 800 nm pump-400 nm probe and 400 nm pump-800 nm probe, respectively. As sketched in Suppl. Fig. 5b, we present the KER distribution for the resonance transition induced by the 800 nm probe pulse, between the $C_4H_5N^{2+}-H_2O$ and $C_4H_5N^+-H_2O^+$ states. In the negative delay region, we present the KER distribution for two different time intervals: $-(40-85)$ fs and $-(200-255)$ fs. The counts for the second time interval are scaled by a factor of 1.2 for better comparison. A sharp and narrow peak centered at 3.1 eV appears in the first time interval, which is absent for the second time interval. Aside from this peak, the distributions are almost identical for both time intervals. This sharp peak, marked by the purple box in Suppl. Fig. 5a, shows characterized energy and temporal features, which is assigned to the resonance transition of 800 nm pulse. As the time delay increases to the second time

Suppl. Fig. 3. Measured and calculated KER for the proton transfer channel $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$. Both experimental techniques are compared with NAMD simulations with the XMS-CASPT2/cc-PVDZ method initiated in S_1 and T_0 states. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

interval, the wavepacket propagates out of the resonance region, and this peak disappears.

Suppl. Note 6. Ellipticity-dependent relative yields of direct dissociation and proton transfer channels

In the strong-field experiment, non-sequential double ionization occurs as a result of the laser-induced electron re-collision process, leading to the double ionization of pyrrole-water complex and Coulomb explosion. Relative to sequential double ionization, non-sequential double ionization is strongly suppressed when driven by the elliptical laser pulse, which rules out the electron re-collision because of the large electron drift momentum. To investigate

Suppl. Fig. 4. The calculated two-dimensional relaxed potential energy surface scan for proton transfer in hydrated pyrrole at the electronic ground state of the dicationic dimer. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

the role of non-sequential double ionization, we present the ellipticity-dependent relative yields of the direct dissociation channel and the proton transfer channel. The relative yields of both channels are determined by their counts ratio with the parent ion $(C_4H_5N-H_2O)^+$ in both linear and elliptical laser pulse cases. The results, shown in Suppl. Fig. 6, reveal that the yields for both channels exhibit weak dependence on the ellipticity of the driving laser pulse. Thus, we infer that the sequential double ionization mechanism is dominant in the present experimental condition.

Suppl. Note 7. Time-dependent yield curves of 800 nm pump-800 nm probe measurement

The FWHM of pump and probe pulse used in our measurements is around 35 fs. We obtained a Gaussian instrument response function from the time-delay-dependent single

Suppl. Fig. 5. The time delay-dependent KER distribution. (a) The time delay-dependent KER distribution of the $C_4H_5N^+-H_2O^+$ for two-color pump-probe measurement. The color scale represents the counts, with the purple box highlighting the 800 nm resonance distribution. (b) The KER distributions for two delay time windows: (-40 to -85 fs) and (-200 to -255 fs). The red curve represents a Gaussian fit to the KER data for the -200 to -255 fs window, showing a peak at approximately 3.1 eV. The counts for this time window are scaled by a factor of 1.2 for comparison. Error bars indicate statistical uncertainties in the measurements and were calculated by the square root of the true coincidence counts. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

ionization of He, and the estimated instrument response time is 45 fs. In the fit of the time-dependent ion yield curve, the convolution of the exponential decay function and Gaussian instrument response function has been used to include the influence of instrument response. Moreover, the instrument response time is inserted in the yield curve for comparison, as shown in Suppl. Fig. 7a. It is shown that the measured yield curve exhibits long tails extending beyond 100 fs, indicating that the underlying dynamics extend beyond the instrument response time. The fitted decay time is closely associated with this long tail and reflects the overall trend of the spectral distribution. The decay time constants for the positive and negative regions are 29 ± 11 and 29 ± 15 fs, respectively. When we apply a moving average to smooth the yield curve and fit the smoothed data with the same function, the corresponding decay time constants are 34 ± 5 fs and 31 ± 6 fs, respectively, as shown in Suppl. Fig. 7b. A comparison between (a) and (b) reveals that the two sets of decay time constants are consistent within the error bars. The scattered points in the yield curve of Suppl. Fig. 7a lead to the larger error bars of the fit. Within this error range, we infer that

Suppl. Fig. 6. Ellipticity-dependent relative yields of direct dissociation channel and proton transfer channel in our measurement. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

the decay time of the prepared wavepacket should be within 50 fs.

In Suppl. Fig. 8, we present the fit with a Gaussian instrument response function as the orange line. The deviation between measurement and fit is significant in the long tail region, from 50 fs to 150 fs or -50 fs to -150 fs. If we fit the yield with a Gaussian distribution, the obtained FWHM is 84 fs, which is about twice the instrument response time. The deviation between the measured data and fit remains evident, particularly in the long tail region and near the peak around zero. The comparison between Suppl. Fig. 7 and Suppl. Fig. 8 suggests that the yield contains an exponential decay feature with a very small decay time constant.

Suppl. Note 8. The KER distributions and time-dependent yield curves of the proton transfer channel in 800 nm pump-400 nm probe measurements

To further support our 800 nm pump-400 nm probe scheme, we present the KER distributions of the high-energy region (3.2-4.4 eV) of the competing $C_4H_4N^+ + H_3O^+$ channel in the 800 nm pump-400 nm probe experiment for both positive and negative time delays.

Suppl. Fig. 7. Time-dependent yields of the $C_4H_5N^+ + H_2O^+$ channel. (a) Time-dependent yields of the $(C_4H_5N^+ + H_2O^+)$ channel measured with an 800 nm pump-800 nm probe scheme. The whole spectrum including both the negative and positive sides is fitted with two exponential decay functions convoluted with the instrument response function. The instrument response function is also inserted for comparison. (b) Smoothed yield curve by the move mean function. With the same function, two decay time constants are obtained. The original data and the smoothed data exhibit the same scale of decay time constant. Error bars indicate statistical uncertainties in the measurements and were calculated by the square root of the true coincidence counts. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

As shown in Suppl. Fig. 9a, the additional 3.9 eV peak observed in the positive time delay region of the $C_4H_5N^+ + H_2O^+$ channel is absent here. Moreover, the time-dependent yield curve (Suppl. Fig. 9b) in the 3.8-4.1 eV region (same as in Fig. 4e in the main text) exhibits a structureless distribution, which is in sharp contrast to that of the $C_4H_5N^+ + H_2O^+$ channel (Fig. 4e in the main text). This result verifies the validity of the PT time analysis based on the time-dependent yield curves of the $C_4H_5N^+ + H_2O^+$ channel in the 3.8-4.1 eV region.

Additionally, for the 800 nm - 400 nm pump-probe measurement, we also presented the time-dependent yield curves for the high-KER tail of the $H_3O^+ + C_4H_4N^+$ channel (3.2-3.5 eV) to compare with Fig. 4e of the main text. Here, the same level of statistics is presented. As shown in Suppl. Fig. 10, the yield curve is symmetric for negative and positive time delay, which can be well fitted by the Gaussian instrument response function (IRF). The

Suppl. Fig. 8. The smoothed curve is fitted with the Gaussian functions. The difference between the experimental data and the fit is shown as the residual. Error bars indicate statistical uncertainties in the measurements and were calculated by the square root of the true coincidence counts. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Suppl. Fig. 9. KER versus delay time spectra. (a) The KER distributions of the high-energy region (3.2-4.4 eV) of the $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$ channel in the 800 nm pump–400 nm probe experiment for both positive and negative time delay regions. (b) Time-dependent yield curve in the 3.8-4.1 eV region of the $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$ channel. Error bars indicate statistical uncertainties in the measurements and were calculated by the square root of the true coincidence counts. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Suppl. Fig. 10. Time-dependent yield curves of the $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$ channel within the KER range of 3.2-3.5 eV. Error bars indicate statistical uncertainties in the measurements and were calculated by the square root of the true coincidence counts. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

temporal feature of the yield curve for the $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+ + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+$ channel is dramatically different from that of the $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}^+$ channel, as expected. This result further supports that our time-dependent yield curve shown in Fig. 4e of the main text is adequate to extract accurately the PT timescale within the current experimental uncertainty.